

**FINITE ELEMENT MODELING OF LAYUP PROCESS
WITH HEAT TRANSFER AND DEFORMATION OF CFRTP**M. Nishikawa^{1*}, Y. Naito¹, N. Matsuda¹ and M. Hojo¹¹ Dept. of Mechanical Engineering and Science
C3 KyotoDaigaku-Katsura, Nishikyo-ku, Kyoto, 615-8540, Japan
Email: nishikawa@me.kyoto-u.ac.jp, <http://ams.me.kyoto-u.ac.jp>**Keywords:** CFRTP, Simulation, Process Modeling, Heat Transfer**ABSTRACT**

The present study examined a coupled simulation of the transient heat transfer and viscoelastic deformation of the materials during the thermal processing of CFRTP, using finite element method. The simulation assumed both elastic and viscoelastic matrices for CFRTP, and the results were compared. The simulated results revealed that the compaction stress applied during the layup process was nearly constant under the present simulation conditions, and the roller contact force determined the stress introduced in the tapes during the layup process.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the manufacturing process using a large-scale monolithic molding technique of the structures made of carbon-fiber reinforced composites, automated layup techniques [1-3] have been widely examined. Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) have been expected for the use from the viewpoint of their processability and reparability, because of their characteristics that the phase change between solid and liquid phases is reversible, and that the molding is possible by local heating. In the processing of CFRTP, the applied pressure is necessary during the consolidation process. In order to prevent the microcrack initiation inside the material, the molding of the material should be made at its melted state under a sufficiently high temperature. In contrast, the process window becomes narrow so as not to cause the thermal decomposition of the matrix resin at a high temperature. Therefore, it is desirable to establish reliable molding methods with a precise temperature and pressure control.

Especially, there are unknown factors about the damage initiation inside the materials under the conditions of a high temperature and an externally applied pressure. For example, Kitaguchi [4] confirmed the microcrack initiation under a high temperature and an externally applied pressure even near the melting temperature, when the thermoplastic resin (for example, PA6 (Polyamide 6) that has a low yield stress and shows a nonlinearity) was used for the matrix. Kanesaki et al. [5] found the critical viscosity between the solid and melted states of the resin by comparison between the experiment and FE (Finite Element) analyses assuming the squeeze flow of an incompressible non-Newtonian fluid. Thus, the previous analytical investigations [1-2] using PEEK (Poly Ether Ether Ketone) as the thermoplastic material mainly for use in aircraft structures should consider the range of application, and in general, the temperature control considering the internal stress during the processing is required. For this purpose, it is required to establish simulation techniques in order to understand and monitor the internal state (temperature and stress state) of materials during the thermal molding process of CFRTP.

The present study examined a method to analyze the heat transfer and viscoelastic deformation of the materials during the thermal processing of CFRTP, using coupled simulations based on finite element method. The layup process of a tape material, seen in the automated fiber placement (AFP) process, was modeled as an example of the state-of-the-art manufacturing techniques. In order to investigate the effect of material properties on the stress distribution inside the tape material, the layup process was simulated in the cases assuming the material as an elastic or a viscoelastic material for the comparison.

2 NUMERICAL PROCEDURE

Coupled simulations of transient heat transfer and structural analyses considering the heat conduction and viscoelastic deformation (temperature-dependent) properties were conducted using a commercial finite element analysis solver MSC.Marc. The schematic of the numerical model was shown in Fig. 1. The materials were assumed as CF/PEEK (APC2) and a unidirectional layup was assumed. The present simulation assumed the layup process of the heated material on the heated flat-plate mold by a consolidation roller while applying heat and pressure. The situation was considered as an example model. In real applications, an external heating source, including a hot gas torch, laser heating, flash lamp heating and so on, is used to achieve the local heating of the material near the compaction roller, and the initial and boundary conditions will be changed in order to reproduce these cases.

2.1 Transient heat transfer analysis

In the transient heat transfer analysis, the basic two-dimensional equation was used in the following form,

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k_x \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + k_y \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + Q \quad (1)$$

with the following boundary conditions of heat flux q , considering the radiation term to the atmosphere (1st term) and the heat transfer term to the atmosphere, flat plate, or between the materials (2nd term).

$$q = \varepsilon \sigma (T^4 - T_0^4) + h(T - T_0) \quad (2)$$

Here, T , ρ , c , k , and h denote temperature, density, specific heat, heat conductivity, and heat transfer coefficient, respectively. T_0 is the atmospheric temperature. The lower cases of x and y denote the directions of coordinate system axes. σ and ε denote Stefan Boltzmann constant and emissivity, respectively. The source term Q was neglected in the present analyses.

The contact heat transfer ($100 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$) and the proximity radiation (surface emissivity 0.1) between the rigid roller ($350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and the material, the heat transfer ($7 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$) and radiation (emissivity 0.9) between the material and atmospheric environment (20 K), the contact heat transfer ($100 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$) and proximity radiation (0.9) between the laminated materials and incoming material during the layup process, and the constant heat flux by the heat transfer between the materials and the mold ($q_0 = 25 \text{ kW/m}^2$) were considered. The initial temperature of the materials was set as $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and the heat conduction properties of the materials were referred to the literature values [1-3] for PEEK (APC2), and the materials were assumed as orthotropic; heat conductivity $k_L = 6.0 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$ (longitudinal), $k_T = 0.72 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$ (transverse), density $\rho = 1.56 \text{ g/cm}^3$, specific heat $c = 1425 \text{ J/kg}\cdot\text{K}$.

2.2 Viscoelastic deformation analysis

In the deformation analysis of the materials, the materials were assumed as orthotropic viscoelastic materials. The viscoelastic constitutive law was defined as follows.

$$\sigma_{ij}(t) = \int_0^t G_{ijkl}(t - \tau) \frac{d\varepsilon_{kl}(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau + G_{ijkl}(t) \varepsilon_{kl}(0) \quad (3)$$

$$G_{ijkl}(t) = G_{ijkl}^\infty + \sum_{n=1}^N G_{ijkl}^n \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\lambda^n}\right) \quad (4)$$

where t is time. σ_{ij} , ε_{ij} , G_{ijkl} , G_{ijkl}^∞ , G_{ijkl}^n and λ^n are stress, strain, relaxation modulus, equilibrium modulus, modulus contribution for each relaxation time, relaxation time, respectively. In the MSC.Marc software, the relaxation time was assumed as isotropic. The relaxation time was calculated through the definition of a shift factor. The elastic properties were referred to Ref. [1] and the viscoelastic properties (relaxation modulus and shift factor) were determined based on the creep test results in the fiber transverse direction in Ref. [6]. For simplicity, the longitudinal and shear viscoelastic moduli were represented as Prony series approximations with the same relaxation time (1000s: assumed value), and

a single main relaxation term was considered and the moduli were adjusted by the ratio of the instantaneous relaxation moduli. More precisely, it is desirable to evaluate these moduli independently by considering the off-axis creep properties in 15° direction as examined in Ref. [6]. In addition, another more accurate procedure to obtain the relaxation modulus is referred to Refs. [7, 8], which calculated the inverse number in Laplace space from creep properties of the material. In the present analysis, the shift factor which represented the temperature dependence of relaxation time was defined by the following Arrhenius-type equation, and the same values as that of retardation time in Refs. [1, 5] were used in Eq. (5) for simplicity.

$$\ln a_T = \frac{\Delta H}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_{\text{base}}} \right) \quad (5)$$

Here, R is the ideal gas constant, and T_{base} is the base temperature (370 K) for $a_T = 1$. ΔH is the formation enthalpy during the relaxation process, and it has a different value below and above the base temperature T_{base} . The glass transition temperature T_g of the material is approximately 145°C and the melted temperature is 345°C [1].

2.3 Analytical conditions

The analysis was conducted until the roller moved on the distance of 40 mm (analysis time: 4 s, time step: 4 ms). The analysis employed large deformation analysis (total Lagrangian formulation) with dynamic implicit method (single step Houbolt method). Prior to the analysis, the tape material was placed so as to touch the circular arc with an angle of 45° on the outer periphery of the roller at the initial state, as shown in Fig. 1. The contact conditions were considered between the roller and the material and between the materials, and the friction at the contacted interface was ignored. The diameter of the roller was 40 mm, translational velocity was set to be $v_x = 10$ mm/s, and the applied total force to the tape material was kept constant as $F_y = 40$ N. In the actual tape layup process, there occur complicated phenomena; the friction between the materials tends to generate the wrinkling of the tape, for example. The present study mainly focused on the stress of the tape material due to the compaction, neglecting complicated three-dimensional deformation of the tape material. The thermal expansion and contraction of the tape materials were neglected. For simplicity, the material that was already laid up was completely fixed to the mold plate. The right end of the material was fixed in x -direction. It should be noted that the friction and thermal mismatch between the mold and the tape material affects the deformation of the tape material, which was neglected in the present analyses.

Figure 1: Model for thermoplastic composite tape process (Unit: mm).

In the finite element analysis, the model was divided into four-node plane-strain quadrilateral elements. The total number of nodes was 1025, and the total number of elements was 920. The stress distribution inside the material during the layup process was compared between the elastic and viscoelastic materials for the properties of the tape material.

3 NUMERICAL RESULTS

Figure 2 presents the results of stress and temperature distributions obtained by the viscoelastic analysis. During the roller movement process, the stress applied to the materials was almost constant. In the figures, t denotes the time after the roller started to move in the horizontal direction. The compressive normal stress in y -direction applied to the laminated materials was nearly constant during the layup process. The stress inside the tape to be laid up was higher than that inside the laminated materials. The effect of cooling of the materials was considered to be minimal because the temperature dependence was small as explained later. In real applications, a tape material is subject to the tension in the fiber direction, and thus, the stress state is more complicated than that predicted in the present analyses.

Then the simulation was conducted assuming the elastic materials for the tape and the laminates. By comparison between the results for the viscoelastic and elastic materials in Fig. 3, it was found that there was no significant change observed and the influence of the temperature-dependence was limited according to the present model. The figures in Fig. 3 correspond to the results at time $t = 1$ s after the roller movement. In both the models, the compressive normal stress in y -direction applied to the laminated materials was similar within the range of -1.0 to -0.3 MPa. One potential reason is the precision of the viscoelastic analysis. Even so, according to the results, it is required to control the applied pressure of the roller, rather than the temperature control, in order to eliminate the microcrack initiation inside the materials.

Although the results may be dependent on the relative balance between the layup speed and the material properties of shift factor and relaxation time, it was implied that the temperature control is not effective in order to eliminate the microcrack initiation. Even at a high temperature, an out-of-plane stress is applied to the material, and thus the applied pressure by the roller should be controlled. Moreover, the temperature rise reduces the elastic modulus of the material, which may cause difficulties in retaining the configuration of the tape material and become a source of fiber waviness.

Figure 2: Results for dynamic thermo-viscoelastic simulation.

Figure 2 (Continued): Results for dynamic thermo-viscoelastic simulation.

Figure 3: Comparison of the results between the viscoelastic and elastic materials.

The results were obtained with one example model assuming the fictitious heating condition. In the state-of-the-art laser heating, the tape and the laminates are locally heated near the roller contacted area, and the effect of the temperature on the materials will be minimal. Considering the complicated boundary conditions in real applications, the effect of temperature and pressure conditions on the tape materials should be investigated further in relation to the material properties.

In the present analyses, the relaxation properties and the shift factor were determined based on the data of creep test results. Thus, no significant temperature dependence appeared in the simulated results, because the phenomena near the melting temperature was little reflected in the simulations. Instead, appropriate material properties of CFRTP near the melting temperature should be determined in the case of the in-situ consolidation process of CFRTP, where the fusion bonding near the melting temperature is essential at the interface between the tape and the laminates. Here, the previous literature [4, 5] concluded that the elastic properties of the fibers had an effect on the deformation of the CFRTP material even near the melting temperature. Macroscopic viscous flow constitutive law proposed in the past (such as [9]) should be determined in relation to the fiber architecture and microstructure of CFRTP materials (stacking sequence, volume fraction of the fibers, fiber dispersion, fiber waviness and so on) for the complete understanding of the deformation mechanism. The microstructure-dependent properties will be clarified by a squeeze-flow experiment and a mesoscale model of the laminates, and the simulations with the material properties appropriately determined will improve the discussion during the layup process of CFRTP materials.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The present study examined a coupled simulation of the transient heat transfer and viscoelastic deformation of the materials during the thermal processing of CFRTP, using finite element method. The coupled simulation provides the information of temperature and stress distributions inside the material. The temperature is an important parameter for determining the fusion bonding quality and crystallinity of the manufactured material, while the stress determines the probability of microcrack initiation and some quality defects including fiber misalignment and waviness.

The analyses assumed both the elastic and viscoelastic matrices for CFRTP, and the results were compared. The compaction stress by the layup process was nearly constant under our simulation conditions, and the roller contact force determined the stress introduced in the tapes during the layup process. In real applications, the generation of fiber misalignment tends to be suppressed by the applied tension to the tapes even in the existence of the out-of-plane stress; however, the microcrack initiation should be eliminated by controlling the internal stress generated inside the material during the layup process.

In contrast, the present analysis has an issue in determining relaxation properties at a high temperature, because actual CFRTP materials have a drastic state change between solid and liquid states near the melting temperature. In the future discussion, material models for heat conductivity and viscoelastic model must be appropriately determined. The actual layup process allowed by the state-of-the-art automated process in composites manufacturing introduces a more complicated phenomenon. For example, a steering layup using thermoplastic tapes involves complicated three-dimensional deformations including in-plane shear steering and out-of-plane compaction deformations. Additionally, if the target surface is a contoured surface, the contact force is not always applied in the transverse direction of the laminates, and thus the conditions for generating fiber waviness and misalignment will become difficult to determine. A suitable model should be developed for three-dimensional coupled simulations of transient heat transfer and material deformations. It is still difficult to be modeled, and therefore, it will be left as an issue to be discussed in the future study.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Part of this work was supported by JSPS KAKENHI 16K06885. We acknowledge the support of Academic Center for Computing and Media Studies (ACCMS), Kyoto University for the analyses with their supercomputer system.

REFERENCES

- [1] F.O. Sonmez and H.T. Hahn., Process modeling of heat transfer and crystallization for thermoplastic composite tape placement, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, **10**, 1997, pp. 198-275 and 381-414.
- [2] S.M. Grove, Thermal modelling of tape laying with continuous carbon fibre-reinforced thermoplastic, *Composites*, **19** (5), 1998, pp. 367-375.
- [3] W.J.B. Grouve, *Weld strength of laser-assisted tape-placed thermoplastic composites*, PhD. Thesis, University of Twente, 2012.
- [4] N. Kitaguchi, *Evaluation of flowability for fibers and matrix in CFRTP with continuous fiber reinforcement under thermal fusion bonding conditions*, Master Thesis, Kyoto University, 2015, (in Japanese).
- [5] M. Kanesaki, N. Kitaguchi, M. Nishikawa, M. Hojo, Relation between viscosity and flow characteristics in uni-directional CF/PA6 laminates near the melting point, *Journal of the Japan Society for Composite Materials*, **44** (5), 2018, pp. 173-182 (in Japanese).
- [6] X.R. Xiao, C.C. Hiel, and A.H. Cardon, Characterization and modeling of nonlinear viscoelastic response of PEEK resin and PEEK composites, *Composites Engineering*, **4** (7), 1994, pp. 681-802.
- [7] T. Sakai, *Creep analysis based on linear viscoelastic theory of thermoplastic resin and its composites*, Doctor Thesis, Keio University, 2008, (in Japanese).
- [8] M. Arai, H. Tanaka, K. Matsushita, K. Tada, Y. Kawakubo, and K. Sugimoto, Numerical simulation and characterization of press molding of thermo-plastic resin reinforced by carbon nanofiber, *Journal of the Society of Materials Science, Japan*, **57** (8), 2008, pp. 814-819 (in Japanese).
- [9] A.J. Beaussart, J.W.S. Hearle, R.B. Pipes, Constitutive relationships for anisotropic viscous materials, *Composites Science and Technology*, **49**, 1993, pp. 335-339